

E-commerce in Bangladesh: Exploring the Challenges and Prospects of Online Shopping amid the Pandemic

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Abstract

The COVID-19 pandemic has been raised as a new concern in the world, which poses several uncertainties in every aspect of human life. In particular, it has drastically affected the business and economic sectors around the world. Due to the pandemic, people have changed their purchasing behavior from the traditional concept. The principal aim of this study was to explore people's perceptions of using online shopping during the pandemic. This study has also investigated the major challenges and prospects of online shopping during the pandemic. The study was conducted using a quantitative approach. Following stratified random sampling, a total of 320 people participated in the cross-sectional survey that used online shopping during the pandemic. The findings reveal that Bangladesh has provided a favorable atmosphere to carry out e-commerce activities, whereas 55% took advantage of e-commerce, 90% of the respondents had a device at their disposal to access online shopping, 68% had a stable internet connection, and 41% were satisfied with the quality of online shopping services. In contrast, some challenges were also identified, including that 82.5% of respondents faced the dilemma of using unreliable online platforms, 60% faced fraudulent activities, 68.75% faced payment complexity, and 72% faced high internet costs. The study findings suggest that the government and concerned authorities (the Ministry of Commerce) should adopt new technologies, build digital infrastructure, ensure logistics capabilities, establish reliable e-commerce platforms, ensure high-speed internet access, and build a collaborative relationship with stakeholders to address the issues of online shopping in Bangladesh. However, future research may focus on facilitating the growth and resilience of the e-commerce sector while leveraging emerging opportunities in a post-pandemic landscape.

Key Words: COVID-19 Pandemic, E-Commerce, Online Shopping, People's Perception, Challenges, Prospects, Bangladesh.

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1. Introduction

The term "e-commerce," which stands for "electronic commerce," describes the exchange of products and services through the internet. It includes conducting business transactions between companies themselves or between companies and customers utilizing digital technologies, including websites, mobile applications, social media platforms, and online marketplaces (Yue, 2022). Besides, e-commerce is the practice of purchasing or offering goods and services over computer networks or other electronic systems that guarantee the transactions (Pallavi Dinodia, 2018).

E-commerce has brought about a revolutionary transformation in the world's trade and commerce systems, particularly in the fields of internet marketing, online transaction processing, mobile commerce, electronic funds transfer (Ahmed et al., 2023), electronic data interchange (EDI), inventory management systems, etc. (Kütz, 2016). Moreover, e-commerce has transformed the way consumers make purchases and enabled firms to reach a worldwide audience. Using e-commerce platforms, customers may peruse a vast selection of items and services, compare prices, make secure payments, and get doorstep delivery (Ning et al., 2018).

In particular, the trade and commercial sectors have been severely impacted by the recent COVID-19 pandemic. Also significantly altered by COVID-19 are the ways in which consumers and commercial organizations conduct their operations. E-commerce is now playing a big part in this respect to support many company sectors globally (Donthu & Gustafsson, 2020). However, e-commerce may be divided into four categories: business-to-business (B2B, like Cisco), business-to-consumer (B2C), consumer-to-consumer (C2C), and business-to-government (B2G) (Danish Khan et al., 2014).

Particularly in Bangladesh, C2C platforms like bikroy.com and clickbd.com, as well as B2C e-commerce sites like ajkerdeal.com and bdbazar.com, are now significantly contributing to the nation's economy as e-commerce sites. Developing countries have more potential than developed countries to improve company structure and boost efficiency using e-commerce as a medium (Khan, 2020).

Due to the advancement of e-governance (Ahmed, 2023), in particular m-commerce (Mobile Commerce) (Cao et al., 2015) and f-commerce (Facebook Commerce), the number of online transactions has grown and improved in this respect over time (Leong et al., 2018). The Bangladesh Telecommunications Regulatory Commission (BTRC) reports that more than 80 million people in Bangladesh now have access to the internet, indicating the expansion of e-commerce. According to current data, around 2,000 e-commerce sites and 50,000 Facebook-based stores supply almost 30,000 things daily (Khan, 2020).

Common types of e-commerce in Bangladesh

Figure 1: Common types of e-commerce in Bangladesh (Islam, 2018)

Despite having started in the late 1990s, the e-commerce industry was unable to grow fast. Following that, banking, logistics, communications, and payment systems all gradually became better after 2000. Since customers may now use credit, debit, and digital wallet services, the cash-on-delivery technique has become more widely available. People who have access to the internet have increased in number as internet connections have become better (Lin, 2017). However, the e-Commerce Association of Bangladesh (e-CAB) projects that by 2021, the e-commerce business would have grown to Tk 70 billion (Khan, 2020).

Despite the fact that the e-commerce industry has expanded over time, there are still a number of obstacles, including a lack of internet neutrality, a slow internet connection, insufficient logistics for package delivery, fraud, data security issues, difficult payment

processes, and the need to ensure that the goods are of a high standard, among others (Nazir & Roomi, 2021). Furthermore, foreign e-commerce platforms compete with and harm homegrown startups (Khan, 2020). In this sense, e-commerce operations in Bangladesh may be improved by foreign investments, low-cost, high-speed internet, safe transactions, enough logistic support, and robust e-commerce laws (Wang et al., 2020). In order to assess the existing difficulties and future potential of online buying, the main goal of this research was to examine the state of e-commerce during the pandemic in Bangladesh.

2. Aim and Objectives of the Study

The principal aim of this research was to examine the status of online shopping during COVID-19 pandemic in the context of Bangladesh.

The specific objectives of the study were-

- a) To identify the status of online shopping amid the pandemic in Bangladesh.
- b) To explore the challenges of online shopping in Bangladesh regarding online shopping.
- c) To elucidate the prospects of online shopping in Bangladesh.

3. Literature Review

Due to the devastating coronavirus pandemic, the globe is now experiencing dreadful times (Ahmed & Akter, 2021). Every country on the globe is battling jointly against the COVID-19 pandemic. In addition, the COVID-19 pandemic has delivered an unforeseen shock to the world economy as well as international trade and business (Canuto, 2020). In particular, rising markets and developing economies have faced unique obstacles due to the devastating impact of the pandemic. In this regard, e-commerce is now playing a crucial role in sustaining economic activity and mitigating COVID-19's tremendous impact (Alwan et al., 2023). However, in Bangladesh, e-commerce operations continue to be hindered by a variety of obstacles.

Algamash et al. (2020) investigate a study on the factors, such as perceived risk, social influence, performance expectation, and effect expectation that influence customers' e-loyalty and usage of e-commerce during the pandemic. The study finds that there is a strong correlation between impact expectations, social influence, and the enabling environment for e-commerce, and customer loyalty is a crucial component of any company's long-term success and expansion. However, the study suggests that online firms should look at the three factors—effect expectation, social influence, and enabling condition—that are linked to the use of e-commerce in a good way (Algamash et al., 2022). Besides, a study on the development of e-commerce during the COVID-19 pandemic by FitzHerbert (2020) emphasizes how COVID-19 has had a severe impact on people's consumption patterns and way of life. He notes that despite the strong lockdown of COVID-19 (the curfew), which caused many businesses to shut down and millions of people to lose their employment, there are many enterprises associated with e-commerce strategies that are expanding. He also suggests that strong e-commerce laws, digital transaction control, and transparency would stimulate the use of e-commerce around the world (FitzHerbert, 2020). Similarly, Nyrop et

al. (2020) discuss the expansion of e-commerce activities in the midst of the pandemic, which helps e-commerce enterprises grow globally. The COVID-19 pandemic, according to the study, has significantly altered people's attitudes toward online transactions and shopping. Many businesses are struggling to survive as a result of the COVID-19 situation, but online businesses have an advantage due to e-commerce. The study also provides a number of recommendations that are critical for the current and future of the e-commerce industry. For instance, new distribution strategies, logistics capabilities, heightened online competition, improved supply chains and fulfillment, technological prowess, improved customer experiences, and the development of digital business models can all be crucial to the transformation and successful operation of an e-commerce business (Nyrop et al., 2020). Conversely, Kawasaki et al. (2021) conduct a study on the use of e-commerce during the COVID-19 pandemic. The study investigated the consumers' behavior and intention to use e-commerce during the pandemic. The study findings reveal that during the COVID-19 outbreak, grocery online sales increased immediately. On the other hand, the industrial and software industries' revenue has immediately boosted after the pandemic. Moreover, findings also demonstrate that, with the blessings of e-commerce, during the lockdown, people are having the opportunity to spend more time at home, whereas they are missing the opportunity to do shopping at a retail store. However, the study claims that the COVID-19 outbreak has increased consumer adoption of e-commerce (Kawasaki et al., 2022). As well, Neger and Uddin (2020) undertake a study to investigate the variables that impact customers' internet shopping behavior in Bangladesh during the Corona virus pandemic. According to the results of the research, the payment element, the time-saving aspect, the security factor, the product quality factor, and so on, influence the consumer's decision to purchase online in Bangladesh. The research used a quantitative methodology and non-probability sampling techniques to acquire data. In conclusion, the research reveals that the COVID-19 pandemic condition in Bangladesh has a beneficial effect for e-commerce (Meher Neger & Burhan Uddin, 2020). Correspondingly, Pejić-Bach (2021) explores a study on the perspective and challenges of using e-commerce during the pandemic. Initially, the study explains the drastic effect of the pandemic on the different business entities. Then the study highlights the major perspectives and challenges of using e-commerce during the pandemic. Despite the many benefits of e-commerce, the survey demonstrates that privacy and security, inadequate capacity for the delivery of products and services, and insufficient mobile connection were the greatest challenges to e-commerce use during the pandemic (Pejić-Bach, 2021).

Although different researchers and writers have written extensively on the significance of e-commerce in recent years, but a preliminary literature analysis reveals that no study has been undertaken to examine the present state of e-commerce in Bangladesh in light of the pandemic.

In particular, the researcher would like to mention that in previous studies, Neger and Uddin (2020) conducted their study based on non-probability sampling and demonstrated the benefits of online shopping amid the pandemic in Bangladesh, but they did not explore the challenges of online shopping amid the pandemic. Moreover, no particular research has yet been undertaken to examine the existing challenges and prospects of online

shopping in the context of the pandemic. Even yet, no exhaustive recommendations have been made to overcome the current obstacles of e-commerce and online purchasing in Bangladesh.

In contrast, the previous research differs significantly from the proposed study in terms of the study area, sample, techniques, variables, and data collection approach. In addition, the majority of the study was initially guided by secondary sources. Therefore, the setting of this study was vital for determining the current situation of e-commerce in Bangladesh in the midst of the pandemic by analyzing the challenges and prospects of online shopping.

4. Materials and Methods

The study was based on a quantitative approach. Information was gathered for this esteem from both primary and secondary sources. The study was conducted in the different areas of Mymensingh district, including Bhaluka Upazila, Trishal Upazila, and Mymensingh Sadar Upazila. However, the respondents were housewives, day laborers, employers, businessmen, non-government employers, students, and government employers. On a random-cluster basis, using both a virtual instrument (a Google form) and an offline instrument (a face-to-face interview), primary data were collected from 320 customers who make purchases online, while secondary data were compiled from a wide range of publications, including books, articles, reports, websites, and newspapers. To collect survey data and examine the current state of online shopping in Bangladesh, closed-ended questions were used.

The main reason behind choosing the quantitative approach was that it allowed researchers to conduct statistical analysis of data (Demetrius Madrigal, 2020). However, within the framework of this research, the concept of validity pertains to the extent to which the methodologies used for data collection and analysis adequately include the complexities and potentialities associated with online shopping during the pandemic in Bangladesh. This process included using suitable survey inquiries, interviews, or observational methodologies that effectively capture the experiences and perspectives of individuals engaged in online shopping and stakeholders. In contrast, to establish reliability, this study used the same data collection methods and analysis protocols across different samples and periods. This allowed the results to be repeated and the findings to be applied to Bangladesh's e-commerce environment during the pandemic.

In particular, the stratified probability sampling strategy was used in this study to gather data. Target respondents for this study were customers who shopped through different internet platforms. The researcher fundamentally conducted a field survey to contact the intended respondents. However, a total of 320 respondents were used as a sample unit to obtain survey data. As the study was directed based on a quantitative methodology, the collected data were systematically arranged, and the coding operations were completed. However, by following descriptive approach of data analysis, organized data were statistically examined and presented in the report in accordance with the results using the software packages "MS Excel" and "SPSS" (Miočić et al., 2020).

Correspondingly, the study presents and analyzes data using univariate analysis. Moreover, the study was scientifically related to the moral and ethical values of social obligation (Žukauskas et al., 2018). Since ethical issues have a definite connotation owing to the detailed nature of the research procedure, this research was steered by following research ethics. Confidentiality, harmony before interviews, voluntary participation in the survey, and respondents’ secrecy were preserved firmly (Yip et al., 2016).

5. Findings of the Study

On the basis of a cross-sectional survey, this section significantly examines the existing status of online shopping in the context of the pandemic in Bangladesh. This research presents and analyzes data using univariate analysis. Bar charts, column charts, and pie charts were used in this presentation to display the essential facts. Predominantly, percentage analysis and frequency distribution have been applied to present the data.

5.1 Demographic Information

In every research project, demographic information is regarded as essential since it indicates the general status and circumstances of the subjects. However, the following sections include demographic information about the respondents' gender, age, and occupation.

Table 1: Demographic Analysis

Variables		Frequency	Percent (%)	Cumulative Percent (%)
Gender	Female	160	50	50
	Male	160	50	100.0
Age Range	25-35	216	67	67
	36-50	104	33	100.0
Education Level	Basic Education	92	5	5
	Secondary Education		42	47
	Higher Education/Graduation	124	50	97
	Illiterate	84	3	100.0

[Source: Field Survey in Bhaluka Upazila, Trishal Upazila, and Mymensingh Sadar Upazila, Mymensingh; Jun–July 2021]

According to the survey (shown in table 1), gender distribution showed that there were 50% male (n = 160, 50%) respondents and 50% female (n = 160, 50%) respondents, a balance gender representation, who participated in the survey in terms of assessing the status of online shopping activities in Bangladesh during the COVID-19 pandemic. Similarly, according to the study, 67% of the respondents (n = 216, or 67.5%) who belonged to the age group 25–35 participated in the survey (shown in figure 2), while the rest of the respondents (n=104, 33%) belonged to the age group 36–50. This number unequivocally demonstrates that throughout the pandemic, the majority of Bangladesh's adults used e-commerce services like online shopping. Additionally, according to the survey results, the majority of respondents—50% (n = 160) and 42% (n = 136)—had good educational backgrounds, completed their secondary education and graduation, and were able to use smart

technologies to purchase from online platforms. Conversely, only 5% (n = 16) of the respondents having basic education (shown in Table 1) were able to use smartphones to purchase from the online platform. These statistics demonstrate convincingly that the majority of educated individuals used the e-commerce service (online shopping) throughout the outbreak of the pandemic.

Table: 2 Profession of the Respondents

Profession of the Respondents					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Day Labor	4	1.3	1.3	1.3
	Govt. Employer	20	6.3	6.3	7.5
	Students	164	51.3	51.3	58.8
	Non-Govt. Employer	16	5.0	5.0	63.8
	Businessman	60	18.8	18.8	82.5
	Housewife	56	17.5	17.5	100.0
	Total	320	100.0	100.0	

[Source: Field Survey in Bhaluka Upazila, Trishal Upazila, and Mymensingh Sadar Upazila, Mymensingh; Jun–July 2021]

In addition, based on the survey data, it was found that most of the respondents were students (n = 164, 51%), whereas 19% (n = 60) were businessmen, and 17% (n = 56) were housewives (shown in table 2). This statistic indicates that people who were involved in business and who were housewives or students used online shopping more than other people during the pandemic in Bangladesh.

5.2 Present Status of Online Shopping in Bangladesh amid the Pandemic

This section significantly demonstrates customer perceptions and the present status of online shopping amid the pandemic in Bangladesh by examining several factors, including customer knowledge on e-commerce, i.e., trend in online shopping, device availability, stable internet connectivity, quality of e-commerce service, and satisfaction with service delivery time.

Table: 3 Knowledge about Online Shopping

Knowledge about online shopping					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	320	100.0	100.0	100.0

[Source: Field Survey in Bhaluka Upazila, Trishal Upazila, and Mymensingh Sadar Upazila, Mymensingh; Jun–July 2021]

The results show that individuals are interested in online shopping since it allows for online buying. According to the survey data, it has been found that 100% of the respondents were well acquainted with online shopping amid the pandemic since they were well educated (most of them were undergraduates and graduated) and experienced in using online shopping before the pandemic, which clearly indicates the positive e-commerce status in Bangladesh (shown in table 3).

The reason behind this argument is that Bangladesh has already gone through with implementing Vision 2021-Digital Bangladesh, which facilitated improving the digital atmosphere of trade and commerce in Bangladesh and is also aligned with the concept of positive e-commerce status in Bangladesh.

Figure 4: Device Availability to Access Online Shopping

[Source: Field Survey in Bhaluka Upazila, Trishal Upazila, and Mymensingh Sadar Upazila, Mymensingh; Jun–July 2021]

The survey data demonstrates that the majority of respondents (n=288, 90%) had a device at their disposal to access online shopping, while just a small percentage (n=32, 10%) did not have a device at all (shown in figure 4). The above figure clearly demonstrates that there is a favorable e-commerce environment in Bangladesh for doing online business.

Figure 5: Stable Internet Connection

[Source: Field Survey in Bhaluka Upazila, Trishal Upazila, and Mymensingh Sadar Upazila, Mymensingh; Jun–July 2021]

Regarding exploring the current status of e-commerce in Bangladesh, the researcher investigates the stability of the internet connection. In this regard, figure 5 demonstrates that around 68% of respondents (n = 218) enjoyed a stable internet connection while purchasing goods from several online platforms.

Conversely, it was also found that one-third of the respondents (n = 102, 32%) face internet connection challenges while they engage in online shopping activities (shows in figure 5). Therefore, these results suggest that in order to promote e-commerce in Bangladesh, problems with unstable internet connections should be resolved.

Figure 6: Trend in Online Shopping during Pandemic

[Source: Field Survey in Bhaluka Upazila, Trishal Upazila, and Mymensingh Sadar Upazila, Mymensingh; Jun–July 2021]

In terms of assessing the users' perceptions of online shopping, the researchers tried to explore the trend of online shopping during the COVID-19 pandemic. The findings of the study reveal that more than half of the respondents ($n = 176$, 55%) took advantage of e-commerce as well as online shopping during the COVID-19 pandemic in Bangladesh (shows in figure 6).

In contrast, despite awareness of and access to internet shopping, a startlingly high proportion of respondents ($n = 144$, 45%) chose not to do so (shown in figure 6). However, trustworthiness concerns were the biggest worry in this aspect. The results show that most respondents did not utilize internet purchasing during the pandemic because of trust worries.

Figure 8: Satisfaction on Product Quality

[Source: Field Survey in Bhaluka Upazila, Trishal Upazila, and Mymensingh Sadar Upazila, Mymensingh; Jun–July 2021]

Correspondingly, the author also assessed people's satisfaction with product quality in e-commerce (online shopping). In this regard, the survey data reveals that 41.3% ($n = 132$) of the respondents were satisfied with the product quality, whereas a notable number of

respondents (20%, n = 64) were dissatisfied with the product quality in online shopping (shown in figure 8).

Surprisingly, 38.8% of the respondents (n = 124) did not share their experience in this aspect. However, these findings highlight that product quality in online shopping is now a great concern to the consumer in the country. Hence, there is no other option but to increase product quality in order to increase people's trustworthiness while purchasing online.

5.3 Major Challenges of Online Shopping amid the Pandemic in Bangladesh

This section significantly illustrates the existing challenges of e-commerce in Bangladesh amid the pandemic. The challenges include unreliable websites for e-commerce activities (online shopping), poor product quality, high cost of the internet, complex payment systems, delays in service delivery, fraud activities, etc.

Figure 9: Unreliable Online Shopping Websites/Platforms

[Source: Field Survey in Bhaluka Upazila, Trishal Upazila, and Mymensingh Sadar Upazila, Mymensingh; Jun–July 2021]

Unreliable websites for e-commerce or online shopping are also seen as a big problem for online shopping in Bangladesh. In this respect, 82.5% (n = 264) of the respondents believe that most Bangladeshi e-commerce platforms are not completely reliable. Even though this problem had doubled during the pandemic period in Bangladesh (shown in figure 9).

The study's findings indicate that consumers have little faith in the existing online shopping platform. Therefore, concerned authorities (government, ministry of commerce, and ministry of economics) should concentrate on developing a trustworthy e-commerce marketplace in Bangladesh.

Figure 10: Poor Product Quality

[Source: Field Survey in Bhaluka Upazila, Trishal Upazila, and Mymensingh Sadar Upazila, Mymensingh; Jun–July 2021]

In the context of this study, it was also revealed that poor product quality was another issue with online shopping in Bangladesh. According to study results, 39 percent (n = 125) of respondents said that they often got inferior goods while making purchases online during the pandemic (shown in figure 10). This finding indicates that the issue of product quality perplexed customers when making any online purchase. On the other hand, 37% of the respondents (n = 117) said that they did not have any problems with product quality while making online purchases (shown in figure 10). This finding indicates that many web-based organizations continue to provide high-quality goods. Therefore, the researcher contemplates that in favor of enhancing online shopping activities in Bangladesh, concerned authorities should prioritize fixing the issues of product quality in online shopping.

Figure 11: High Cost of Internet

[Source: Field Survey in Bhaluka Upazila, Trishal Upazila, and Mymensingh Sadar Upazila, Mymensingh; Jun–July 2021]

The high cost of the internet is also considered a major issue for online shopping in Bangladesh. While utilizing various online platforms during the pandemic, the survey data reveals that the majority of respondents (72.5 percent, n = 232) faced problems with internet costs (shown in figure 11).

These statistics indicate that Bangladesh lags behind most of its neighbors in offering affordable or free internet access to its residents. However, 14% (n = 44) of respondents were neutral, and the remaining 14% (n = 44) did not think that internet costs were high. These statistics suggest that they might make use of inexpensive internet services offered by private internet providers. However, the overall findings indicate that customers in Bangladesh thus desire affordable internet so that they can easily connect to numerous online shopping platforms.

Table 4: Complex Payment System

Complex Payment System			
		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Yes	220	68.75
	No	80	25
	No comment	20	6.25
	Total	320	100.0

[Source: Field Survey in Bhaluka Upazila, Trishal Upazila, and Mymensingh Sadar Upazila, Mymensingh; Jun–July 2021]

Consumers are also concerned about complicated payment procedures while purchasing online. The study results show that 68.75% (n = 220) of the respondents had payment troubles when making purchases from online shopping platforms during the pandemic (shown in table 4). While 25% (n = 80) of the respondents said that they had no problems paying online, the problems with online payment must be resolved as soon as possible so that customers may make purchases without difficulty (shows in table 4).

Figure 12: Delay in Service Delivery

[Source: Field Survey in Bhaluka Upazila, Trishal Upazila, and Mymensingh Sadar Upazila, Mymensingh; Jun–July 2021]

This study also looks into the service delivery issues associated with online shopping. According to the field survey, 75% of respondents i.e., (n=240) who made online

purchases during the pandemic on various e-commerce platforms in Bangladesh experienced service delivery delays (shown in figure 12). There are no other options to address the problem of delayed delivery in this context and increase the trustworthiness of the online shopping platform for general customers.

Figure 13: Fraud Activities

[Source: Field Survey in Bhaluka Upazila, Trishal Upazila, and Mymensingh Sadar Upazila, Mymensingh; Jun–July 2021]

Fraud activity is one of the most discussed and troubling aspects of online shopping in Bangladesh. In this respect, 60% (n = 192) of respondents believe that fraudulent activities on various internet platforms in Bangladesh are now the talk of the town for the general public (shown in figure 13).

People do not have any faith in online shopping due to deceptive activities. Thus, the author believes that the perpetrator must be punished by the relevant authorities, and an example must be set for fraud campaigners.

5.4 Prospects of Online Shopping amid the Pandemic in Bangladesh

Amid the pandemic, Bangladesh's e-commerce sector has witnessed significant growth and adaptation. The shift towards online shopping has been accelerated, fostering a digital marketplace. Increased internet penetration, changing consumer behavior, and a growing preference for contactless transactions have fueled this surge. E-commerce platforms i.e online shopping has become essential for businesses to reach customers, ensuring a resilient and dynamic market.

Despite challenges, the prospects for e-commerce in Bangladesh remain promising, offering a convenient and safe alternative for consumers and fostering economic resilience. In this vein, this section delineates the prospects of e-commerce amid the pandemic in Bangladesh.

Figure 14: Customer Interest on Online Shopping during Pandemic

In terms of assessing the prospects of online shopping in Bangladesh, people’s perception has been investigated by the author. According to the survey data, it was found that 92% (n = 294) of the respondents were interested in shopping online during the pandemic (shown in figure 15).

[Source: Field Survey in Bhaluka Upazila, Trishal Upazila, and Mymensingh Sadar Upazila, Mymensingh; Jun–July 2021]

The finding clearly indicates the prospects of online shopping in Bangladesh, since the majority of respondents express their interest. In addition, the researcher believes that since Bangladesh is now reaping the benefits of digitalization and information and communication technology (ICT), individuals should get the benefits of online shopping.

Figure 15: People’s Perception about Online Market

[Source: Field Survey in Bhaluka Upazila, Trishal Upazila, and Mymensingh Sadar Upazila, Mymensingh; Jun–July 2021]

In terms of assessing the people’s perception of online shopping, the majority of respondents i.e., 85% (n = 272) believe that online shopping initiatives and operations are on the increase in Bangladesh, while just a few believe that online shopping performances are declining (shown in figure 16). However, the data shows that the online shopping platform is doing well despite the fact that a number of challenges remain.

Figure 16: Reliable E-Commerce Platform can enhance the Public Trust on Online Shopping

[Source: Field Survey in Bhaluka Upazila, Trishal Upazila, and Mymensingh Sadar Upazila, Mymensingh; Jun–July 2021]

Reliable web platforms, including e-commerce sites, were among the most talked-about issues during the pandemic. Due to the pandemic, the majority of people were isolated in Bangladesh; hence, they utilized a variety of internet platforms to buy their daily essential goods. In this situation, the findings reveal that the majority of customers experience fraud on phony e-commerce sites. In light of this, the survey's results show that 83% (n = 268 of participants argue that a trustworthy online platform may be valuable for both e-commerce and regular consumers in Bangladesh under any circumstance (shown in figure 16). Therefore, it is important for the concerned authorities to concentrate on establishing and approving trustworthy e-commerce platforms as well as operations in Bangladesh.

Table: 6 IT Infrastructure is Essential to Fix the Issues of E-commerce

IT Infrastructure is Essential to Fix the Issues of E-commerce					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	260	81.25	81.25	81.25
	No	28	8.75	8.75	8.75
	No Comment	32	10	10	100.0
Total		320	100.0	100.0	

[Source: Field Survey in Bhaluka Upazila, Trishal Upazila, and Mymensingh Sadar Upazila, Mymensingh; Jun–July 2021]

The assessment of the state of online shopping in Bangladesh during the pandemic was the main goal of this research; hence, IT infrastructure is a closely related topic. According to the results, 81.25% (n = 260) of the respondents agree that a solid IT

infrastructure may improve online shopping activities in Bangladesh and help it run more smoothly (shown in table 6). These results suggest that infrastructure support and development are very necessary to make the e-commerce platform functional in Bangladesh.

6. Discussion of the Study

The COVID-19 pandemic has had a major effect on the business sector in Bangladesh (Ahmed, 2021), presenting both possibilities and obstacles (Ahmed, 2020). As people try to avoid congested physical shops and reduce their exposure to the virus, the pandemic has resulted in a rise in demand for online purchasing and home delivery services. In this context, the e-commerce sectors in Bangladesh now have the chance to grow their client base and increase their revenue streams. Therefore, this study has clearly demonstrated the state of online shopping, its prospects, and the challenges in Bangladesh during the pandemic. It was found that 90% of respondents have access to a device for online shopping, 68% of respondents had a stable internet connection while purchasing goods from multiple online platforms, and 55% of respondents utilized online shopping during the COVID-19 pandemic in Bangladesh. These statistics demonstrate that Bangladesh has a favorable e-commerce environment for conducting online business. In this regard, the investigations of Algamash et al. (2020), Nyrop et al. (2020), and Sumarliah et al. (2021) provided substantial support for the findings. Similarly, 41% of the respondents were satisfied with the product quality, and 48.8% of the respondents were satisfied with the product delivery time during the pandemic, which is consistent with the findings of (FitzHerbert, 2020; Nyrop et al., 2020; and Sumarliah et al., 2020).

In contrast, the pandemic has also posed significant challenges for the e-commerce sector in Bangladesh. E-commerce companies' bottom lines have suffered as a result of supply chain interruptions, organizational difficulties, and constraints in the digital infrastructure. In addition, customer distrust in online purchases has been a major problem, with low acceptance rates in some regions brought on by worries about product quality, shipping schedules, and return policies (Gupta et al., 2023). Consequently, the research reveals that 83% of respondents believe that the majority of Bangladeshi online shopping platforms are unreliable. 56% received inferior goods while making online purchases during the pandemic; 72% encountered issues with internet costs; 69% had payment issues; 75% encountered service delivery delays; and 60% encountered fraudulent activities on various internet platforms, which demonstrates the existing challenges of e-commerce and online shopping in Bangladesh. Peji-Bach, 2021; Galhotra and Dewan, 2020; Beyari, 2021; present their arguments in support of the current difficulties of online purchasing in Bangladesh during the pandemic.

To address these challenges, online shopping in Bangladesh need to invest in digital infrastructure and logistics capabilities, adopt new technologies and business models, and collaborate with stakeholders to create a more enabling environment for online transactions. These efforts can help businesses overcome supply chain disruptions and logistical challenges and improve the efficiency and security of online transactions. Increasing digital literacy and promoting consumer trust in online transactions are also critical factors that can

help drive growth in the online shopping activities in Bangladesh. This can be achieved through awareness campaigns, digital training programs, and transparent and reliable information about product quality, delivery times, and return policies. Moreover, government agencies and industry associations can play a vital role in creating a supportive environment for online shopping in Bangladesh by providing regulatory support, financial incentives, and policy reforms that enable businesses to thrive. Collaboration between stakeholders can also help address challenges such as digital infrastructure limitations and promote the development of a sustainable online shopping ecosystem that benefits businesses, consumers, and the economy as a whole. In conclusion, the challenges and prospects of online shopping in Bangladesh amid the pandemic require a concerted effort from all stakeholders to overcome the obstacles and seize the opportunities presented by the sector. By investing in digital infrastructure, enhancing logistics capabilities, adopting new technologies and business models, and collaborating with stakeholders, online shopping in Bangladesh can build a resilient and sustainable ecosystem that benefits all stakeholders.

7. Conclusion and Recommendations

The COVID-19 pandemic has had a big effect on Bangladesh's e-commerce industry, creating both problems and opportunities. On one hand, the pandemic has increased demand for online shopping and home delivery services, leading to a surge in e-commerce transactions. In this vein, fraud activities, unreliable websites for e-commerce, poor product quality, delays in service delivery, the high cost of the internet, complex payment systems, and security issues have been identified as significant obstacles for online shopping. To overcome these challenges, online shopping activities in Bangladesh need to invest in digital infrastructure and logistics capabilities, adopt new technologies and business models, and collaborate with stakeholders to create a more enabling environment for online transactions. Additionally, efforts should be made to increase digital literacy and promote consumer trust in online transactions to further stimulate growth in the e-commerce sector. Despite the challenges, the e-commerce industry in Bangladesh has tremendous growth potential, and the pandemic has provided an opportunity for businesses to innovate and adapt to changing consumer behaviors. By embracing the opportunities presented by e-commerce and addressing the challenges, Bangladesh can build a robust and sustainable online shopping ecosystem that benefits businesses, consumers, and the economy as a whole.

Based on the challenges and opportunities highlighted in this research on online shopping in Bangladesh during the pandemic, the following suggestions can assist businesses and stakeholders in addressing the challenges and capitalizing on the opportunities:

Firstly, to ensure quick and easy purchasing, online shopping in Bangladesh should invest in digital infrastructure development like secure and strong internet access, safe payment platforms, and cloud-based storage options. In this regard, the study survey has also demonstrated that 83% of participants argue that a trustworthy online platform may be valuable for both online shopping and regular consumers in Bangladesh. Besides, 81% of the respondents agree that a solid IT infrastructure may improve e-commerce sectors in

Bangladesh. Moreover, 60% of the respondents believe that high-speed internet may entice customers to engage in online shopping, which would help Bangladesh's e-commerce industry.

Secondly, working together with government organizations, business groups, and other stakeholders can help Bangladesh's e-commerce sector thrive. This can involve e-commerce business regulation assistance, cash rewards, and policy changes. In this vein, 95% of the respondents argue that government affirmative action can address the different issues of online shopping in Bangladesh.

Thirdly, to combat supply chain problems, online shopping businesses in Bangladesh should build strong logistics capabilities including last-mile transportation services, real-time response, real-time monitoring, and effective inventory management, etc.

Fourthly, to improve the speed and security of online operations, online shopping companies should adopt cutting-edge technologies including artificial intelligence (AI), machine learning, and blockchain. In addition, businesses should explore new business models such as social commerce (Facebook marketing) and subscription-based services to diversify their revenue streams.

Fifthly, to encourage the usage of online purchasing and house delivery services, efforts should be made to improve customer digital knowledge. This can include awareness campaigns, digital training programs, and user-friendly interfaces, etc.

Finally, online shopping companies should put strong security measures in place, such as two-factor identification, encryption, and safe payment channels, to promote customer confidence in online purchases. In order to earn customers' confidence, online shopping companies should also offer honest and trustworthy information about product quality, shipping schedules, and refund policies. By implementing these recommendations, online shopping businesses in Bangladesh can address the challenges posed by the pandemic and build a more resilient and sustainable e-commerce ecosystem that benefits all stakeholders. However, future research may concentrate on letting the e-commerce industry expand and become more resilient while taking use of new possibilities in the post-pandemic environment.

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